

STRESSES IN THE VICINITY OF A DEBOND IN A LAMINATE
VIA SHEAR DEFORMABLE PENALTY FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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Abstract

This paper details the unique coupling of a shear deformable solid finite element formulation with the penalty function for predicting interlaminar shear and normal stresses in thick composite laminates and near bonded and debonded free edges in laminated plates. An improved interlaminar shear stress variation is achieved by integrating the equilibrium equations through the thickness of the laminate. Utilized to represent continuity or discontinuity, the penalty function acts like a very stiff spring between layers of elements. A simple and efficient method is obtained for investigating three-dimensional stresses near debonds. Different sizes of debonds are examined in a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminated plate without having to create a new model by simply adjusting the value of the penalty parameter, which represents the "spring constant" of the penalty function.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Finite Element Analysis; Shear; Plates; Laminate.

1. Introduction

Stress analysis of laminated composite plates is generally complicated due to the orthotropy of composite materials and the different fiber orientations of the laminae. Exact or closed-form solutions exist for only a small category of problems, which contain simple lay-ups, boundary and loading conditions. Therefore, numerical modelling techniques derived from energy principles are often utilized for the stress analysis of fiber-reinforced materials. Specifically, the finite element method adapts well to problems of complex geometry, constraint and loading conditions.

Engblom, Fuehne and Hamdallah(1) have reported on research focusing on computing the interlaminar shear and normal stresses by integrating the equilibrium

equations as an alternative to using the constitutive equations. This feature, developed by Engblom and Ochoa(2), is applicable to thin to moderately thick laminated structures and, when combined with a shear-deformable finite element formulation, produced significantly improved predictions of interlaminar stresses through the thickness.

Additionally, these formulations have been further extended to thick plates and shells by employing penalty functions to layer plate elements through the thickness(3,4). In this capacity, the penalty functions provide continuity through the thickness at interelement boundaries by behaving as very stiff springs connecting the two elements. The penalty parameters represent the "spring constants" of the penalty functions. Adjusting the value of the penalty parameters provides versatility in the formulation. Setting the penalty parameter equal to a very large number represents continuity but if the penalty parameter equals zero then a discontinuity is modelled. Similarly, varying the magnitude of penalty parameter may allow analysis of problems of plasticity or crack growth.

The coupling of the penalty functions with a twenty-noded solid formulation has been demonstrated by Fuehne and Engblom(5) to be effective in analyzing thick composite plates and in predicting stresses near a bonded and debonded free edge. In this work, the flexibility of the penalty function method is demonstrated by investigating interlaminar stresses near a free edge containing debonds of several sizes. This is accomplished by creating only one model and varying the magnitude of the penalty parameters.

It is notable that Lagrange multipliers may be used in a similar fashion as the penalty functions to maintain continuity through the thickness. However, Lagrange multipliers, because they add degrees of freedom to the system, are inefficient when compared to the penalty function and do not provide the flexibility of the penalty function. Chatterjee and Ramnath(6) have used the Lagrange multiplier in their efforts to model laminated structures as an assemblage of sublaminates. In this case, a sublaminar, by their definition, is equivalent to one layer of elements in the proposed work. Although Chatterjee and Ramnath do not consider thick plates and shells, they do study laminated plates with delaminations(7).

Although Engblom and Fuehne(3,4) illustrated the benefits of coupling the penalty functions with the integration of the equilibrium equations for the eight-noded plate element, in order to effectively model problems which contain significant variations in interlaminar normal stress through the thickness, a twenty-noded solid formulation is developed. Of particular interest is the unique coupling of the solid element formulation and the integration of the equilibrium equations to obtain interlaminar stress predictions. As a result of the transverse displacement being a function of the through the thickness coordinate, it is expected that the integration of the equilibrium equations will be effective in modelling the free edge problem. Additionally, the penalty functions are also included in the formulation so that

problems with discontinuities, like the double cantilever beam or a laminated plate with a debond at the free edge, may also be investigated.

2. Displacement Variation

The formulation of the twenty-noded solid element is similar to that described by Cook(8). Each of the twenty nodes contains three displacements but rotations are omitted. The displacement in the x direction, in terms of nodal displacements and shape functions, is given by

$$u(x, y, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{20} N_i(\xi, \eta, \zeta) u_i \quad (1)$$

Utilizing these shape functions guarantees a tri-quadratic variance of displacements for the solid element. For example,

$$u = u(1, x, y, z, xy, xz, yz, xyz, \dots, x^2yz, xy^2z, xyz^2). \quad (2)$$

The calculation of the solid stiffness matrix uses a layer by layer approach that is capable of handling orthotropic plates with different fiber orientations or different materials for the layers. Evaluation of the stiffness matrix is performed by integrating over the volume of the element and using a procedure similar to the trapezoidal rule:

$$[K] = \sum_{k=1}^{NL} \left(\int_{-1}^{+1} \int_{-1}^{+1} [B]^{kT} [D]^k [B]^k \|J\|^k d\xi d\eta \right) \quad (3)$$

where NL is the number of layers in the element. It should be noted that as the summation proceeds from layer to layer, matrices $[B]$ and $[J]$ are calculated for each layer and the matrix of material properties, $[D]$, is modified based on fiber orientation. The above integral is evaluated using 3×3 Gauss quadrature for all strain energy components - no shear locking effects are evident with the solid element.

2.1 Constraint Equations

Writing the constraint equations for the solid element is quite simple. Figure 1 shows two stacked twenty-noded solid elements. Since, the solid element has nodes which lie on the interface between the elements, the constraint equations for nodes 1 and 2 in Figure 1 for the displacement in the x direction is

$$u_1 - u_2 = 0. \quad (4)$$

Similar equations are derived for the displacements in the y and z directions. In matrix form, including all displacements, the constraints are

$$[C]\{\delta\} = [0]. \quad (5)$$

where $[C]$ is a matrix of constants and $\{\delta\}$ is a vector of degrees of freedom.

Implementing the penalty functions to provide the constraints is quite simple. The energy functional is modified with

$$\Pi^* = \frac{1}{2}\{\delta\}^T[K]\{\delta\} - \{\delta\}^T\{R\} + \frac{1}{2}[C]^T\{\delta\}^T[\alpha][C]\{\delta\} \quad (6)$$

and minimizing gives

$$\frac{\partial \Pi^*}{\partial \delta} = [[K] + [C]^T[\alpha][C]]\{\delta\} - \{R\} = 0. \quad (7)$$

As a result of the penalty functions, the stiffness matrix of the finite element method is augmented by the matrix product, $[C]^T[\alpha][C]$. The α term represents the penalty parameters. If α equals zero, then the constraints are ignored; however, as the α grows in magnitude, the constraints are more nearly satisfied. The forces of constraint created by the penalty functions may be approximated by using

$$\{F_c\} = [C]^T[\alpha][C]\{\delta\}. \quad (8)$$

2.2 Penalty Parameters

The $[\alpha]$ matrix in the triple matrix product $[C]^T[\alpha][C]$ is a 3×3 matrix consisting of the penalty parameters on the diagonal and zeroes everywhere else. To add flexibility to the formulation, three penalty parameters are specified: two which maintain continuity of the interlaminar shear stresses through the thickness and a third which maintains continuity of the interlaminar normal stress through the thickness. Specifically, these are referred to as $(\alpha_u, \alpha_v, \alpha_w)$, where the subscript identifies the appropriate continuity through the thickness. There exist situations where there is continuity in the interlaminar normal stress through the thickness, but discontinuity in the interlaminar shear stresses, as in a delamination which is being compressed. The present formulation allows for this by preventing two layers from displacing through each other in the z direction. The penalty parameters α_u and α_v are set equal to zero and α_w is set equal to a very large number.

3. Stress Analysis

3.1 Constitutive Equations

Stresses computed by using the constitutive equations for the twenty-noded element proceed directly from the displacements. The strains are given as

$$\epsilon_x = \partial u / \partial x \implies \epsilon_x = h_1(x, y^2, z^2) \quad (9)$$

$$\epsilon_y = \partial v / \partial y \implies \epsilon_y = h_2(x^2, y, z^2) \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_z = \partial w / \partial z \implies \epsilon_z = h_3(x^2, y^2, z^2) \quad (11)$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = \partial u / \partial y + \partial v / \partial x \implies \gamma_{xy} = h_4(x^2, y^2, z^2) \quad (12)$$

$$\gamma_{xz} = \partial u / \partial z + \partial w / \partial x \implies \gamma_{xz} = h_5(x^2, y^2, z^2) \quad (13)$$

$$\gamma_{yz} = \partial v / \partial z + \partial w / \partial y \implies \gamma_{yz} = h_6(x^2, y^2, z^2) \quad (14)$$

Note that all of the strain components vary quadratically with respect to z . The stresses in layer k are computed using the three-dimensional stress-strain relations, which are expressed in matrix notation as

$$\{\sigma\}^k = [D]^k \{\epsilon\}^k. \quad (15)$$

All of the stress components computed using the constitutive equations are quadratic in all three directions.

3.2 Equilibrium Equations

Integrating the equilibrium equations through the thickness results in a much improved parabolic distributions of interlaminar shear stresses through the thickness of the twenty-noded solid element. As shown above, the stresses computed using the constitutive equations vary quadratically in all three directions. Neglecting body forces, the equilibrium equations are expressed as

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Rearranging these equations to solve for the interlaminar shear stresses yields

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} = - \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} \right) \implies \tau_{xz} = p_1(x^2, y^2, z^3) \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial z} = - \left(\frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}}{\partial y} \right) \implies \tau_{yz} = p_2(x^2, y^2, z^3). \quad (19)$$

This shows that integrating the equilibrium equations does provide an improved variation of interlaminar shear stresses through the thickness.

Computing the partial derivatives of the equilibrium equations relies on the smoothing functions derived for the in-plane stresses. The smoothing functions are based on the values of the in-plane stresses at the Gauss points. Cook(8) documents that, for the quadratic solid element, the location of the optimal points for stress calculation are the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ Gauss points. Since stresses are computed for each layer for the solid element in the present work, Gauss points in the transverse direction are not used. A detailed investigation was undertaken to determine the optimal points of

stress calculation and the results verified that the 2×2 points were optimal for stress calculation. With only four points of stress calculation, bi-linear smoothing functions of the form

$$\sigma_{xx} = C_0 + C_1\xi + C_2\eta + C_3\xi\eta \quad (20)$$

are derived for the in-plane stresses. The bi-quadratic variance through the thickness of the in-plane stresses is implicit to the formulation.

Partial derivatives with respect to ξ and η of the in-plane stresses are easily computed for each layer from the smoothing functions and the inverse of the Jacobian matrix is used to transform them into partial derivatives with respect to x and y . Equation (18) is rewritten for the j^{th} layer as

$$\Delta\tau_{xz_j} = - \left(\frac{\partial\sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial\tau_{xy}}{\partial y} \right)_j \Delta z_j \quad (21)$$

where $\Delta\tau_{xz}$ represents the change in interlaminar shear stress from the lower to upper surface of layer j and Δz_j is the thickness of layer j . The right hand side of equation (21) is known based on the derivatives of the smoothing functions for layer j and the thicknesses; hence, in shortened notation, the right hand sides are denoted by I_{xz_j} and I_{yz_j} . Then, for the j^{th} layer, equation (21) becomes

$$\tau_{xz_{j+1}} - \tau_{xz_j} = I_{xz_j}. \quad (22)$$

For a laminate which is continuous through the thickness, the lower and upper surfaces are shear-free surfaces. Writing equation (22) in matrix notation for n layers yields

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tau_{xz_2} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \tau_{xz_n} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} I_{xz_1} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ I_{xz_n} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

Equation (23) represent n equations in $n - 1$ unknown transverse shear stresses at the layer interfaces. Utilizing a least squares orthonormalization procedure, equation (23) is solved for the shear stresses at the layer interfaces. This procedure is similarly performed to solve for τ_{yz} at the layer interfaces as well.

Computing the interlaminar normal stress from equilibrium, however, is not beneficial. Creating bi-linear smoothing functions for the transverse shear stresses from equilibrium and integrating gives

$$\frac{\partial\sigma_{zz}}{\partial z} = - \left(\frac{\partial\tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial\tau_{yz}}{\partial y} \right) \implies \sigma_{zz} = p_3(x^2, y^2, z^2). \quad (24)$$

Since there is no benefit from integrating the equilibrium equations, all interlaminar normal stress results presented herein are computed using the constitutive equations.

4. Results

4.1 Continuous Laminates

Although the penalty functions are not necessary for three-dimensional analysis with the solid element, the coupling of the solid element and the integration of the equilibrium equations to compute interlaminar shear stresses is unique, and continuous problems were studied to evaluate this feature. Results generated for thick laminates subjected to cylindrical and sinusoidal bending were presented by Fuehne and Engblom(5). Significant improvement is observed with the addition of multiple layers, and the integration of the equilibrium equations is shown to be a more accurate method of computing the interlaminar shear stresses than the use of the constitutive equations. It is notable at this point that Fuehne(9) introduced a detailed comparison of interlaminar shear stresses computed with the constitutive equations and the equilibrium equations in thick composite plates with both the twenty-noded solid element and the eight-noded plate element. For thick plates, the eight-noded plate element formulation consistently provided more accurate interlaminar shear stresses than the twenty-noded element formulation. This is a significant conclusion as the eight-noded plate element, with 48 degrees of freedom per element, is more computationally efficient than the twenty-noded solid element with 60 degrees of freedom per element. As aforementioned, though, the eight-noded plate element is unable to model geometries which contain significant interlaminar normal stress distributions.

Also, free edge analyses were performed for cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates subjected to a uniform axial strain. As reported by Fuehne(9), favorable comparisons were made between the present work and similar analyses by Wang and Crossman(10) and Pipes and Pagano(11). Consistently, the interlaminar shear stresses computed by integrating the equilibrium equations approached the other two solutions more than did the interlaminar shear stresses derived from the constitutive equations. Of course, the solutions developed by Wang and Crossman(10) and Pipes and Pagano(11) are either finite element or finite difference solutions and are considered bench marks for the free edge problem, but are not exact solutions. Additionally, interlaminar shear stress results from the equilibrium equations more closely satisfy the stress-free edge condition in cross-ply laminates than do stresses from the constitutive equations.

4.2 Discontinuous Free Edge Problems

As previously mentioned, the penalty function formulation described herein allows stress analysis of problems with discontinuities through the thickness. Although

there are no available solutions with which to compare, a cross-ply, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ plate with a delamination between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers at the free edge and subjected to a uniform axial strain is considered. The notation and geometry for this problem are given by Figure 2. Three different debond lengths, including one-half, one, and two ply thicknesses from the free edge, are examined in this paper. One model, consisting of 4 layers and 110 twenty-noded elements per layer, is assembled. Through the skillful use of PATRAN(12), a model limiting the use of the penalty functions to certain predetermined critical interfaces is created. Varying debond lengths are obtained by setting the penalty parameters equal to either a large number, representing continuity, or zero, signifying discontinuity. Because of the flexibility of the formulation, models with relatively small bandwidths and storage requirements are possible.

Figures 3-5 present interlaminar normal stress between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers for free edge debond thickness equal to one-half, one, and two ply thicknesses respectively. The 48 and 49 labels in the legend refer to the ply from which the stress values are obtained. As previously described, the stresses from the constitutive equations are computed for each ply. Typically, each layer is subdivided into 24 plies. As a result, the stresses from the constitutive equations are not located at the interface but at the plies on either side of the interface. In this four layer model, there are 96 total plies in which stresses are computed and designations 48 and 49 represent the values adjacent to the center interface. In all three cases, a significant stress magnification, nearly equal to that at the free edge without the debond, is realized at the tip of the debond. The largest interlaminar normal stress occurs for the debond equal to 1 ply thickness. Note that the area between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers and between the free edge and the debond crack tip is a stress-free surface. For this area, an average of normal stresses from either side of the interface gives a value near zero.

Finally, Figures 6-8 reveal the predicted interlaminar shear stress field near the debond between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers for the three different debond lengths. Again, designations 48 and 49 refer to interlaminar shear stresses computed using the constitutive equations on either side of the interface. Interlaminar shear stresses calculated by integrating the equilibrium equations are labeled as EQ. Again, a significant shear stress magnification, which approaches twice that of the bonded free edge value, is observed at the tip of the debond. Close examination of the plot indicates that averaging the interlaminar shear stresses computed using the constitutive equations produces a value approximately equal to those found by integrating the equilibrium equations everywhere except for a short distance near the debond tip and the area beyond the tip. A very important observation is that the free surface between the debond front and the free edge is a shear-free surface. The integration of the equilibrium equations automatically produces zero interlaminar shear stress at those interfaces. The interlaminar shear stresses computed by employing the constitutive equations, however, are not zero on either side of the interface and even an average of the values above and below the interface

does not produce zero stress. Obviously, the interlaminar shear stresses calculated by integrating the equilibrium equations are more realistic than those from the constitutive equations for this problem.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a unique coupling of a twenty-noded solid element formulation, the integration of the equilibrium equations, and a penalty function method is detailed. Interlaminar shear stress predictions through the thickness are improved by integrating the equilibrium equations for thick laminated plates and a cross-ply plate subjected to a uniformly applied strain. By using the penalty functions to represent discontinuity between layers, interlaminar normal and shear stresses are investigated in a cross-ply plate with a debond at the free edge and subjected to a uniform strain. Significant magnifications in interlaminar normal and shear stresses occur at the tip of the debond. A more suitable variation of interlaminar shear stresses is obtained for the debond problem by integrating the equilibrium equations through a stack of elements and accounting for the discontinuity at the debond. The versatility of this penalty function formulation allows the examination of interlaminar stresses near debonds of different sizes with only one model. The magnitude of the penalty parameters is varied appropriately to represent continuity or discontinuity at critical locations in the model. Additionally, the forces of constraint between nodes may be approximated using the nodal displacements with the penalty functions. Ultimately, these forces may be used in a fracture mechanics approach which may include varying the penalty parameters to represent plasticity and to allow for debond growth.

6. References

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FIGURE 1. Two stacked 20-noded solid elements, showing nodes at the common boundary.

FIGURE 2. Geometry and notation for a composite laminated plate subjected to a uniform axial strain in the x direction.

FIGURE 3. Transverse normal stress, σ_z , between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers of a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate subjected to a uniform axial strain with a delamination at the free edge equal to one-half ply thickness.

FIGURE 4. Transverse normal stress, σ_z , between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers of a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate subjected to a uniform axial strain with a delamination at the free edge equal to one ply thickness.

FIGURE 5. Transverse normal stress, σ_z , between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers of a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate subjected to a uniform axial strain with a delamination at the free edge equal to two ply thicknesses.

FIGURE 6. Transverse shear stress, τ_{yz} , between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers of a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate subjected to a uniform axial strain with a delamination at the free edge equal to one-half ply thickness.

FIGURE 7. Transverse shear stress, τ_{yz} , between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers of a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate subjected to a uniform axial strain with a delamination at the free edge equal to one ply thickness.

FIGURE 8. Transverse shear stress, τ_{yz} , between the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ layers of a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate subjected to a uniform axial strain with a delamination at the free edge equal to two ply thicknesses.